

Psalm 81

"the Child within"

O Lord, chaos everywhere!
Like a sinking ship
where new leaks seem to appear constantly.
Hardly has one been patched
when another breaks through elsewhere.

Lord, take form in this room,
let Your form enter this space
through my hands.

We are in the outer wall of fire.
A dense thicket of thorns around the Kingdom.
It is hard, one can advance only with great difficulty,
if one is honest.
As if everything wanted to slow you down,
like shackles or quicksand.

Bound by the children of God.
They protect the Kingdom of Heaven
from those who do not belong there.
Thus they become our salvation,
as we practice mercy.
And we become their salvation,
as we care for them
and keep everything in order.

Therefore, everything you have overcome
is another step toward home,
another step on the little stairway to Heaven.
Narrow, steep, painful, arduous.
That is the right path.
By this will you recognize it.

There we are called
to accept our personal pain.
And each one of us has much to say
about how heavy a thing becomes,
about how heavily suffering itself is taken.

Pain comes from the child within us.
When we are grown up,
the child within us does not understand
the new way of thinking.
And that hurts.

And many want to seize
that childlike world by force.
But that belongs to no one.
Rather, it is about being
brave enough and open enough
to fully accept the child within us,
so that we may become fully human.

And here, in my deepest self,
I look down upon that child
and embrace it with all its pain.
And I, as a child,
embrace myself as an adult.

And this, in turn,
is the mirror of the love of God
the Father for the Son,
and back again.
And all of us are in the unity
of the Holy Spirit...

(from the new Psalms – "The Way of the Open Heart")